

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: AYODEJI****FIRST NAME: UZOMA****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: QUIZ****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 13%

The author used the following software: MSWord 2016 on Windows 10

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. When the writer uses sources of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information, this is known as?

- Plagiarism.**¹
- Copy and paste.
- Referencing.
- Acknowledgement.

2. The following are correct about long quotations with over four lines except?

- Have quotation marks.**²

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1*, 3rd ed. (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 5

² Cleenewerck and Gulma, *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1*, 7.

- Have no quotation marks.
 - Have indention.
 - Look like a separate little paragraph.
3. According to Cleenewerck and Gulma, which of the following is not a rule of thumb for writing papers?
- Write clearly.
 - Be focused.
 - State the main thesis.
 - Always generalize.**³
4. What are the five elements of an argument, according to Turabian?
- Question, reason, claim, evidence, and warrant.
 - Warrant, argument, evidence, reason, and claim.
 - Claim, reason, evidence, acknowledgment/response, and warrant.**⁴
 - Acknowledgment/response, claim, evidence, answer, and reason.
5. Which of the following is not a method to detect the reliability of a source?
- Published by a reputable press.

³ Cleenewerck and Gulma, *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1*, 14.

⁴ Kate L. Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, Ninth edition. (University of Chicago Press, 2020), 58.

- No bibliography if it is a book.**⁵
- Peer-reviewed.
- Frequently cited by others.
6. Which answer is not a reason for citing your research work?
- Materials used are easily located.
- To earn the trust of your readers.
- To rubbish the work of other authors.**⁶
- To reinforce your arguments by using other researchers' ideas.
7. According to Turabian, what are the two citation styles?
- Author-date and reference styles.
- Notes and reference styles.
- Notes and bibliography styles.
- Notes and author-date style.**⁷
8. What is the point at which you present your research ideas to gain approval from a faculty committee to proceed with your study?
- Completed proposal.**⁸

⁵ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers*, 42.

⁶ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers*, 139.

⁷ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers*, 142.

⁸ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (California: SAGE Publications, Inc., 2008), 43.

- Problem statement.
 - Completed dissertation.
 - Research questions.
9. Academic or scholarly writing is a type of writing that has the following elements.
- Clear, concise, precise, and bold.**⁹
 - Concise, bold, without citations, and clear.
 - Precise, ambiguous, bold, and concise.
 - Bold, precise, confusing, and clear.
10. According to European Commission Style Guide English, the two legislative procedures are, namely?
- Draft and special legislative procedures.
 - Regulatory and ordinary legislative procedures.
 - Legal and ordinary legislative procedures.
 - Special and ordinary legislative procedures.**¹⁰

⁹ Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 47.

¹⁰ Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 79.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End*. California: SAGE Publications, Inc., 2008.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 3rd ed. Bangui: Euclid University, 2021.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers. 9th edition. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018.

Deleted: 2018.

Deleted: .

Turabian, Kate L., Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, and The University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff. 2020. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Ninth edition. University of Chicago Press.

Commented [GK1]: What is the difference between this and the one directly above? Both seem to be ninth edition!

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.